

Influence of N source and level on grain yield and plant characters, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Tillers		Height		Grains (no./Panicle)	Straw yield		Grain yield		N use efficiency	Total soil N at harvest
	no./ m ²	Increase over control (%)	cm	Increase over control (%)		t/ha	Increase over control (%)	t/ha	Increase over control (%)		
Control – no N PU	13	–	25	–	149	5.8	–	1.7	–	–	588
37.5	15	14	28	10	159	6.6	13	3.0	76	35	697
75.0	18	40	29	15	164	8.6	48	3.4	98	23	728
112.5	16	23	29	15	170	9.2	59	4.2	142	22	735
Av	16	25	28	13	164	8.1	40	3.5	105	24	720
USG											
37.5	16	28	29	15	169	8.0	39	3.4	100	46	679
75.0	17	35	30	19	186	8.5	47	3.9	127	29	721
112.5	22	71	33	30	188	8.9	53	4.6	165	25	788
AV	18	44	30	21	181	8.5	47	4.0	131	30	729
1% FPDU											
37.5	15	15	27	7	160	7.4	29	3.5	105	48	658
75.0	16	29	29	14	166	7.5	29	3.8	122	28	693
112.5	18	41	29	17	166	8.7	50	4.3	150	23	149
Av	16	28	28	13	164	7.9	36	3.9	126	29	700
	SED	CD	SED	CD		SED	CD	SED	CD		
Control vs root	0.99	2.0	0.56	1.1		0.6	1.2	0.26	0.5		
Source × level	0.77	1.6	0.43	0.9		0.5	1.0	0.20	0.4		
Source × level	1.33	2.7	ns	–		ns	–	ns	–		

Ammonia volatilization from waterlogged soils of North Bihar

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In flooded alkaline soils, fertilizer N is lost to air as ammonia during the first few weeks of submergence. We measured ammonia volatilization with different N sources. Soil was an alkaline sandy loam Entisol with pH 8.4, 0.34% organic C, 221 kg KMnO₄-N/ha, and 31% free

CaCO₃ Urea, lac-coated urea, neem cake and urea mixed 1:1 with green manure were the N sources. Rajendra Dhan 201 was grown in a flooded field in 20-m² plots. A 1.2-cm-diam × 35-cm-tall cylindrical frame covered with plastic bag was placed between rows of rice plants immediately after N fertilizer was applied. A petri dish filled with 100 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ was suspended inside the frame. At 3-d intervals, the petri dish was emptied and the contents were distilled for NH₃ with MgO in a microkjeldahl apparatus. Volatilization loss was calculated based on area.

N losses through ammonia volatilization varied widely among N sources. After 16 d, the cumulative N loss ranged from 38 to 55 g/20 m². Volatilization loss was lowest for the urea-green manure treatment: 10 to 26% of fertilizer N volatilized within 4 d of application (see table). Rate of loss declined substantially over time. Total or cumulative loss in 16 d was between 20 and 30% with different N sources. Associated analysis of floodwater, soil solution, and wet soil indicated that high floodwater temperature, high HCO₃⁻ soil solution concentration, high soil pH, and high electrical conductivity caused high volatilization losses in North Bihar. ☞

Percent N loss through NH₃ volatilization, North Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	% loss of N through volatilization at indicated days after fertilizer application						Cumulative loss (%) in 16d
	0-4 d	4-7 d	7-10 d	10-13 d	13-16 d		
Urea split (45 kg N/ha basal + 22.5 kg N/ha at tillering + 22.5 kg N/ha at panicle initiation)	25 15 ^b 12 ^c	1.8 19 1.8	1.9 1.9 0.4	1.3 1.4 0.8	0.3		29
Urea basal (90 kg N/ha)	26	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.3		29
lac-coated urea basal	25	2.5	1.5	1.1	0.2		30
neem cake-coated urea basal	23	3.0	0.6	0.8	0.4		28
Green manure + urea (1:1)	18	1.0	0.6	0.8	0.2		21

^aEach treatment received 45-45 kg PK/ha. ^bLoss after first urea split. ^cLoss after second urea split.

Evaluation of tractor-drawn puddlers and puddling operations

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In Haryana, most farmers with tractors use mounted, spring-loaded cultivators for puddling. Some also use mounted disk harrows. Rotary blade puddlers, rototillers, and power tillers are